

**METHODOLOGY FOR ORGANIZING TRAINING BASED ON STEAM
TECHNOLOGY IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION
(PRACTICAL LESSON FOR PRESCHOOLERS)**

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Annotation: The article describes the development of a lesson based on STEAM technology for preschool children.

Keywords: STEAM, STEAM set for study human body, STEAM technology in preschool education.

One of the issues that interests our current society is the organization of modern activities in such a way that it interests children from preschool age. We will definitely achieve this with the help of STEAM technology. In the STEAM technology module “We conduct experiments with animate and inanimate nature”, the cognitive processes of children develop in the learning process. After all, as a result of the practical organization of education, children quickly develop attention, memory, intuition, perception, thinking, and imagination. The reason is that children try to implement the new information they have learned with their own hands. In this module, we teach children in three areas:

1. Study of alive nature;
2. Study of inanimate nature;
3. Study of optical phenomena;

The educational module “Experimenting with animate and inanimate nature” allows you to organize the acquaintance of children with the properties of water, air, objects of animate and inanimate nature, optical phenomena.

Module tasks:

- formation of ideas about the world around in experimental activities;

- ✚ awareness of the unity of all living things in the process of visual - sensory perception;
- ✚ formation of ecological consciousness.

Preschool children are not interested in verbal information, they are interested in doing all the work in practice. That is why we organize experiments with children in the form of practical classes on the STEAM technology module “Experimenting with animate and inanimate nature”.

A properly equipped laboratory provides an opportunity to saturate classes on familiarization with the outside world with experiments with animate and inanimate nature, arouse interest in experimental activities, instill initial skills, and conduct independent research.

Experimental activities are based on the following principles:

- ✚ The principle of differentiation and individualization;
- ✚ The principle of natural conformity;
- ✚ The principle of dialogic communication;
- ✚ Sequence principle;
- ✚ The principle of accessibility;
- ✚ The principle of consistency;
- ✚ Development principle;

EXAMPLE:

Educational aspect:

- ✚ Providing general information about the human body to children;
- ✚ “Teaching children the functions of organs;

Developing aspect:

- ✚ development of cognitive processes in children;
- ✚ development of motor skills in children;

Equipment: human body models, toy organs.

1. The teacher gives the children general information about the “human body”.
2. Children are shown a model of the human body (in the form of a toy) (picture

№1).

№1. «Human body»

3. The teacher introduces children to each organ of the human body, the functions of organs. Children are given toys that look like organs (picture № 2).

№ 2. Toys

4. The game “Find the right one” is held with children. The essence of the game is to correctly place the pieces in their places. (picture № 3).

№ 3. “Children’s body” s toy

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